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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document describes recent work developed by EMPOWER WP4 regarding the algorithmic development. A hybrid Algorithms Module combines machine learning and rule-based logic to predict performance, personalize game recommendations, and provide real-time feedback. By interpreting player behaviour and sensor data, EMPOWER offers tailored interventions and actionable insights for children and educators.

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#1. Introduction

In EMPOWER, we propose a new approach to understanding children’s strengths and weaknesses in terms of Executive Functions (EFs) and Emotion Regulation (ER) strategies as predictors for their cognitive abilities, representing a different perspective in terms of intervention and teaching strategies. Specifically, by analysing objective data gathered through the platform, it becomes possible to identify mechanisms that may explain the emergence of challenging behaviours in children with neurodevelopmental disorders (NDDs) and to develop personalised interventions based on their psychological profiles.

The **GameSuite** encompasses all games developed within the project, each designed to train specific **EFs**—such as memory, attention, inhibition, cognitive flexibility, and delay of gratification— as well as **ER strategies**, including emotion naming, recognition, and strategy use. The underlying premise of the GameSuite is that there are meaningful connections between executive functions themselves and the ability to recognize and label emotions. The proposal for the Algorithms Module builds on this assumption to build predictive models of player performance. Specifically, it uses a machine learning model to estimate the likelihood of success in each game level (e.g., Memory Level 1) based on performance in other levels (e.g., Attention Level 2), across all possible level combinations. These predictive insights are then used to recommend the game level with the

Figure 1 – Data Flow Pipeline. The game Listener Captures Time-series data from each game which is then used for next game prediction and Feedback generation

highest probability of fostering improvement. A recommendation engine processes this data over time and enables a personalized and data-driven approach to cognitive training.

In more detail, our approach to Algorithm Development (as discussed in Deliverable 4.2) adopts a hybrid model for creating assessment tools and action elements within the game. This hybrid approach combines machine learning for complex aspects of the system with hand-coded actions for simpler, more deterministic tasks. Theoretical concepts guide the mapping of cognitive functions to game mechanics, defining key events of interest and providing structure to the child's in-game behaviour.

Each game includes a **Listener** component that records time-series player interactions and assigns semantic meaning to interaction patterns. This mapping process, described in Section 2, was developed in collaboration with WP2. The output of each Listener is passed through the ML model to generate a performance prediction in all games. To enhance the learning experience, **next-play recommendations** (Section 4) are designed to help children navigate the *GameSuite* more effectively, ensuring a smoother and more engaging progression through the games. The Algorithms Module is also responsible for generating feedback for both the child and the teacher, as well as processing sensor data to provide insights into the child's engagement. Figure 1 illustrates the data flow pipeline. We end this document with a description of how data from the sensors was used to provide feedback to teachers.

#2. Game Listeners

As detailed in D4.2, theoretical concepts are used to map cognitive functions to the game mechanics of the developed games. Theory not only defines key events of interest within the game but also assigns meaning to the child's behavior, establishing the foundational rules for performance in each game.

Each game in the Game Suite includes a Listener, which records timestamped player interactions and assigns semantic meaning to interaction patterns. The mapping process, described in the following section, was developed in collaboration with WP2.

Mapping Game Mechanics to Game Features

Theoretical concepts serve as the foundation for mapping cognitive functions to game mechanics, based on the assumption that these games are gamified versions of the standardized tasks commonly used to assess executive functions, as detailed in **D4.2**. Theory informs the identification of key in-game events and aids in interpreting the child's behaviour, ultimately shaping the definition of *features* for each game. Since the game-mechanics of different games target the same executive function skills, we hypothesize that the in-game features across different games are interrelated. A summary of features and their meaning is in **Table 1**.

ATTENTION GAME – Mushroom Hunters

“The Mushroom Hunters” game is designed to assess sustained attention by requiring players to press the space bar in response to target stimuli (a mushroom) while ignoring other objects like flowers and sticks. There are 60 trials overall, with 30 % of the stimuli corresponding to the target, presented in random order. The game has three levels, and the duration of stimulus presentation, the time between consecutive stimuli, and the time allowed for a correct response vary by level. The time between the appearance and disappearance of objects is 2.5, 2, or 1.5 seconds, in levels 1, 2, and 3, respectively. Player performance is measured through both **accuracy** and **speed**. Accuracy is calculated as the ratio of correct responses to total trials, adjusted for errors: $(\text{correct hits} - \text{incorrect hits}) / \text{number of trials}$. The game records the number of correct responses to targets, the ability to inhibit impulsive actions (reflected in avoiding clicks on distractors), and reaction times for both correct and incorrect responses. The sub-related skills are: *Impulse Control* and *Delay of Gratification*.

WORKING MEMORY GAME – WoRM

At each one of five trials, a sequence of peppers turns yellow, one at a time, and the child is tasked with sorting the peppers into baskets. The sequence length varies by game level, with 2, 3, or 4 peppers turning yellow in sequence. After sorting, the peppers return to their original green color, and the child must recall and select the yellow peppers in the exact order they appeared. The performance of a child in this game is directly linked to their ability to **remember the correct**

pepper in the correct order across all trials (*order_recall*) and per trial (*order_recall_pertrial*). It is hypothesized that sustained attention and cognitive flexibility may play a role in their ability to identify the peppers (they know which peppers to click, but don't know the order) and the length of the sequence, respectively.

INHIBITION – ReStroop

The goal of this game is to recycle objects correctly. In each of the 12 trials, an object (glass bottle, plastic bottle, or cardboard box) appears alongside three bins: green for glass, yellow for plastic, and blue for paper. One bin opens its lid, and the child must decide if it matches the object by selecting a "V" (correct) or "X" (incorrect) button. Depending on the level, a time limit may apply: no time limit in level 1, 1.5 seconds in level 2, and 1.0 seconds in level 3. Objects may appear with congruent (e.g., green glass bottle) or incongruent colours (e.g., green plastic bottle) according to the original Stroop task. Half of the trials correspond to congruent stimuli and half to incongruent stimuli, presented in random order. We are interested in capturing whether they **process congruent** and **incongruent stimuli** (clicks on correct and incorrect buttons), and how fast **they react** to these situations. The sub-related skills are *Memory* and *Delay of Gratification*.

COGNITIVE FLEXIBILITY – CogFlex

The goal of this game is to sort objects for transport to the farmers' market. The child sorts objects into crates based on one of three criteria: colour (yellow, black, purple, green, or orange), number (one to five), and shape (vegetable, fruit, or flower). In each trial, an object appears alongside 3, 4, or 5 crates depending on the level, and the child must identify and apply the correct sorting criterion. The child must consistently select according to the correct criterion for ten consecutive trials. If an error is made at any point, the count resets to zero and begins again. This process continues until the child successfully completes ten correct responses in a row, at which point the rule changes. The maximum number of trials allowed per rule is 90. We track their ability to **maintain the rule** and the **shifting ability**, i.e., understand when the rule changes and apply a different criterion.

DELAY OF GRATIFICATION – BeeHold

In the BeeHold game, the child has to wait for the beekeeper to appear before collecting the honey. The more time they wait, the more time they have to play a mini-game at the end. The 3 trials have increasing waiting times. In this task, we track the time they wait and make a comparative analysis between trials. The sub-related skills are: *Sustained Attention and Inhibition*.

EMOTIONS – Emotifest

In Emotifest, the child can play three different games: *CornHole*, *EmotionWheel*, and *EggPyramid*. The first two games have similar gameplay. Children are required to identify emotions, demonstrate emotional understanding, and show the ability to avoid maladaptive strategies when resolving unintended situations. The third game focuses on emotion understanding and emotion regulation (strategy choice). These are the three variables that we keep track of in each game.

Table 1 - Game Features considered for each game

Game	Features	Description
Attention	correct_hits, incorrect_hits	Hitting the target and the distractor, respectively
	impulse_control	number of times they did not hit the distractor
	processing_speed	Mean of response time in correct_hits
	Reaction times for correct, incorrect and late responses	A response could be correct in between stimuli
Memory	order_recall	Number of pepper that the child recalls correctly
	wrong_order_recall	Number of peppers correct but in the wrong order
	longest_sequence	Size longest sequence of correct peppers the child can retain in memory

	Reaction times for clicks	Reaction times averaged for each action in the game (pepper sorting and selection).
Inhibition	omissions_errors	Incorrect responses
	Inhibition_score	Correct_responses
	task_congruent	Incorrect responses in congruent situation
	task_incongruent	Incorrect responses in incongruent situations
	resilience	Percentage of trials with no answer
	Reaction time click	Mean reaction times for each action in the game
Cognitive Flexibility	perseverative_responses	Correct_shifts
	rule_maintain	Incorrect responses, excludes incorrect shifts
	set_shifting	Incorrect shifts
	errors	Incorrect responses, including incorrect shifts
	Reaction times clicks	Mean reaction times for each action in game
Delay of Gratification	total_waited	percentage of time waited in the game
	Increasing_wait_time	Indicate if waiting time increased
	Decrease_wait_time	Indicate if waiting time decreased
EmotiFest	Correct_emotions	Identification of emotions
	Understanding_option	Understands or not
	Number_maladaptive	Number of maladaptive selected

#3. Feedback Generation

The Feedback system in EMPOWER follows a typical feedback model architecture (Figure 2), depending on three main elements: Domain Model, Expert Knowledge, and Student Data. The former defines **what** kind of feedback to provide in the context of the game and the goal of interaction. The expert knowledge guides when feedback should be triggered and **who** receives the information. The student situation determines **when** the feedback is triggered.

There are two main approaches to feedback generation: data-driven and expert-driven. *Data-driven* approaches use student data to derive feedback rules, often leveraging machine learning (ML) and natural language processing (NLP) to generate personalized responses. In contrast, *expert-driven* approaches rely on rules crafted by psychologists or education specialists, combining theoretical frameworks with practical experience to determine both the content and tone of effective feedback [1]. While data-driven approaches offer the advantage of highly adaptable and personalized feedback, they typically require time series data to train algorithms that can identify meaningful patterns in a student’s learning history (which was not available in our case). Expert-driven approaches, on the other hand, tend to produce more consistent outputs by using

Figure 2 - The Feedback System Implemented that follows a typical feedback architecture. Adapted from [1]

predefined rules to monitor key variables in the learning process, which are then used to fill text templates and deliver structured feedback.

In **EMPOWER**, feedback on game performance is provided to both players and teachers—the latter through the teacher app. For players, the feedback highlights strengths and areas of difficulty using a supportive and encouraging tone. For teachers, it offers a more detailed overview, outlining all tracked variables related to student performance. All feedback is template-based and carefully curated by psychologists to ensure clarity and consistency.

From an implementation standpoint, the feedback system was developed alongside the learning platform and is both *task-* and *student-adaptive*. It is *task-adaptive* because it aligns with the specific skills targeted by each task, recognizing that different tasks focus on different competencies. It is *student-adaptive* because it monitors individual student performance, activating when a student struggles with a particular skill (as defined by expert knowledge) or when notable strengths are identified.

Teacher feedback

Feedback presented to the teacher intends to uncover the components that are being tracked in the game, as described in **Table 1**, for the attention game. Each tracked variable has a semantic meaning of value to teachers/therapists. A template is used to present a log of the tracked variables. These variables map directly to the concepts described in **Table 1 - Game Features considered for each game Table 1**.

Table 2 - Feedback table for the Attention Game

Variable	Meaning	Feedback
Total Correct Answers	Total Correct answers	The student was able to touch the mushrooms ...% of the time.
Total Incorrect Answers	Total Incorrect answers	The student missed the mushrooms and touched other objects ..% of the time.
Error Present	Incorrect answers when the mushroom IS present (i.e. does not hit mushroom) (REVERSE SCORE)	The student missed the mushrooms ..% of the time. Their sustained attention score is ...% .
Error Absent	Incorrect answers when the mushroom is NOT present (i.e. hits distractors). (REVERSE SCORE)	The student touched other objects ..% of the time. Their impulsivity score is ...% .

Mean RT		
Correct	Mean of the response time in	
Present	CORRECTPRESENT	The student had a response speed of

At runtime, a single sentence is selected to summarize the student’s performance across all tracked variables. An example of this can be found in Table 3. For each sentence, we created three wording variations to ensure variety and naturalness. This was done consistently across all supported languages.

Table 3 - Example of Teacher Feedback for the Attention Game

"The player successfully hit the mushrooms {TCA}% of the time, indicating their ability to focus on the target, resulting in a sustained attention score of {SA}. Additionally, the player touched other objects {TIA}% of the time, earning an impulsivity score of {IS} (1 means able to contain impulsivity). Their average response speed of {RS} seconds highlights their reaction time during the game."
--

Student feedback

Feedback is provided at the end of gameplay as an immediate response to the student’s performance. Feedback is triggered when the child shows some *difficulty* or some *strength* in a particular skill —as guided by the template in

Table 4. Difficulty-based feedback is prioritized over strength-based feedback. We created several equivalent variations of the same sentence.

Table 4 - Feedback Template

Difficulty	"You found it a bit hard to [skill description]. That means [skill] can still get better with practice!"
Strength	"You did really well with [skill]! This shows you're getting really good to [skill description]!"

Table 5 illustrates the tracked variables and the values of certain features that trigger feedback. For example, when the variable measuring Sustained Attention falls below 50% during gameplay, it indicates that the player is experiencing difficulty maintaining focus. In such cases, the game may display feedback such as: "You found it a bit hard to **stay focused for a long time**. That means **that your sustained attention** can still get better with practice!", —as guided by the template in

Table 4. Difficulty-based feedback is prioritized over strength-based feedback.

Table 5 - Feedback Triggers for Sustained Attention

Skill	Skill Description	Game Action	Trigger for feedback [difficulty]	Trigger for feedback [strength]
Paying Attention (Sustained Attention)	Stay focused for a long time	Focusing on the correct mushrooms while ignoring distractors	Below 50%	Above 80%
Self-Control (Impulse Control)	Stop yourself from touching the wrong objects.	Resisting the urge to touch distractors	Below 50%	Above 80%
Quick Thinking (Cognitive Processing Speed)	Spot the mushroom and touch it quickly	Does not hit mushroom when it is present	Above 70%	Below 25%

#4. Performance prediction

Machine Learning has been used to see if it is possible to predict whether students pass or fail a programming course [B]. They aim to move away from self-reports of students by using features from the games to predict students' passing probability. Using the features such as rank, score, and attempts, they manage to reasonably well predict the performance of these students. Although interventions in NDDs consider executive functions and emotional regulation altogether [24], it is unclear how to do this using new technologies. We pose the questions: 1) if we can identify links, based on performance, between different executive functions and emotional regulation gamified tasks, and how sensors affect this, and 2) if executive functions and emotional regulation can be improved by using our approach for individualized recommendation of games (see #5. Recommendation Generation). To support the next-play recommendations (Goal 2), we built ML models to predict the game performance of a student based on the scores obtained by the child in other games. We next describe the pipeline to create ML models: data preprocessing, the modelling approach, and an experimental evaluation of the models. The descriptions of this section are based on [3].

Data

Data was collected from a pilot study in schools in Romania and Portugal in December 2024 - February 2025. The children (N=56) were aged 8-14 years with an NDD diagnosis. The children played all the levels of each game in sequential order (with random game order), except if they did not exceed the performance of 75% in a level. Unforeseen events also stopped game playing, e.g. if a participant was tired or there was a platform error. As working memory and cognitive flexibility are quite difficult games, many children did not pass the performance threshold to transition to level 2 or 3, which led to a substantial data imbalance across levels 1, 2, and 3 in these games.

Features

From the pilot data, we built a transitions dataset N_T for training ML models to predict transitions across games. We considered two types of features: **game-specific features** and **performance features**. The game-specific features are measurements specific to each game (e.g., in the sustained attention game, this includes the number of correct responses for stimuli and for distractors and reaction times). The performance feature was the game-specific feature that correlated the most with other measurements (including questionnaires and traditional measurements). The performance feature is used to simplify the prediction task, so that when predicting from game A to game B, we can represent game B as a single output.

Each row in the transition's dataset has inputs, which represent the game-specific scores of a player at a certain level, and outputs, which are the performance scores for all other games at every level. This means that we are creating a dataset that will allow us to predict the performance from the current game to all other games, if a participant transitions to play any of these games. The performance features are *accuracy*, for the sustained attention game, *order_recall*, for the working memory game, *inhib_score*, for the inhibition game, and *hits*, for the cognitive flexibility game. This way, we have constructed 12 datasets for the game-level pairs. Table 6 shows in detail how many rows each dataset has.

It is noteworthy that the ML models always have the same number of output features. For example, from level 2 we predict transitions to levels 1 and 3, and from level 3 we predict transitions to levels 1 and 2 of the same game. It was designed with the purpose of testing whether back-in-time information can be similarly well-predicted as other transitions, which should be a useful indicator of whether a child should play a lower level of the same game next.

Table 6 - Percentage of Averaged Missing Values per All Models per Feature and Number of rows in each dataset (dataset size).

Game	Output feature	Missing Values (%)	Rows
Sustained Attention	accuracy_level_1	2.96	51
	accuracy_level_2	7.68	47
	accuracy_level_3	5.19	48
Working Memory	order_recall_level_1	8.67	48
	order_recall_level_2	34.18	31
	order_recall_level_3	63.48	16
Cognitive Flexibility	hits_level_1	3.19	52
	hits_level_2	38.98	29
	hits_level_3	49.94	23
Inhibition	inhib_score_level_1	6.23	50
	inhib_score_level_2	23.14	40
	inhib_score_level_3	26.17	37

Data pre-processing

All features (both inputs and outputs) were normalized based on their min-max values as ascribed in the game design. Missing values in each feature were imputed by taking the mean feature value across all games. The average missingness per feature is reported in Table 6.

Machine learning methods

Based on the transition dataset N_T , we trained several types of ML models, often suitable for small datasets: Random Forest Regressor, Linear Regressor, Lasso Regressor, Ridge Regressor, Support Vector Machines and XGBoost. The RF models achieved the best results overall, so we will focus on these results. It is worth noting that the RF model can make multi-target predictions by building many decision trees, where each tree splits the values based on a random subset of features and optimizing multi-target leaves. In the end, these decision trees are summed together into one output. An RF model was built for each level of each game; thus, in total, twelve RF models were created.

Evaluation procedure

To evaluate the ML models, we split the datasets into training sets and test sets by allocating 80% for training and 20% for testing, where the test set is used to evaluate the model. We reshuffled the data 10 times, each time selecting random subsets for train and test, to obtain a better estimate of the model scores. To evaluate the predictions, we calculated the root mean square error (RMSE), given by

$$RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{i=1}^{N_{test}} (\hat{y}_i - y_i)^2}{N_{test}}}$$

Where \hat{y}_i , y_i are the predicted and true outputs for case i respectively, and N_{test} denotes the test set.

Experimental Results

Among all games, the best RF model is for working memory level 1, while the worst model is for working memory level 3. The model that predicts from working memory level 3 is affected by a very small dataset (see **Table 6**). Therefore, this model is not the best representative of all the models we built. The mean RMSEs for all games are shown in **Table 7**.

Table 7 - Mean RSME for all games

Game	Level 1	Level 2	Level 3
Working Memory	0.137	0.179	0.196
Sustained Attention	0.140	0.150	0.168
Cognitive Flexibility	0.171	0.166	0.172
Inhibition	0.139	0.151	0.158

Final Considerations

Despite the diversity of participants, the limited variation in both feature distributions and performance scores (see Table 2) likely hindered the models' ability to learn meaningful patterns and may have introduced bias into our results, as well as limited the generalization of our findings. Yet this challenge may not stem solely from the data: traditional machine learning models such as Random Forests may struggle to account for the idiosyncratic, context-sensitive nature of EF performance — especially when factors like prior training, medication, environment (e.g., light or noise), or even interaction with the game interface may significantly impact behaviour. Section #5

describes the mechanism created to accommodate to individual differences during recommendation generation.

#5. Recommendation Generation

The Recommendation Generator (RG) is an algorithm that uses the output of the Performance Predictor to create a personalized sequence of games, along with appropriate difficulty levels, for upcoming intervention sessions. These recommendations guide the player through different games within the **GameSuite**, enabling targeted practice and supporting the development of their *learning potential*. This approach combines data and theory to guide the sequencing of tasks. Similarly to the performance predictor, the RG is in direct communication with the game suite and the Teacher App. **Figure 3** showcases the general structure of the adaptive RG model. As input, the RG considers all the performance predictions of every game-level combination (P), obtained by employing the machine learning model. The output consists of a list of recommendations with a variable size (a parameter which can be defined in the input - $N_{\text{Recommendations}}$). These recommendations are strings which include the suggested game, the corresponding suggested difficulty level, and a brief justification as to why the algorithm recommended that game-level combination - **Figure 3**. The inner workings of the RG are explained in greater detail in the following paragraphs.

Figure 3 - General structure of the adaptive RG model

First Stage: Learning Potentials

Firstly, the RG loops through every game-level ($G;L$) performance prediction for every game-level played and taken as input by the ML model - these predictions are stored in P , a structure obtained from joining all the outputs of the ML model. On each game-level, each predicted performance ($\rho_{\text{predicted for } G;L}$) is directly compared to the last registered performance ($\rho_{\text{last registered for } G;L}$), thus originating a $\delta_{G;L}$ (1) - the learning potential for that specific game-level match. Every $\delta_{G;L}$ is embedded into a dictionary data structure - Δ - which, by the end of the initial loop, will contain the $\delta_{G;L}$ of every game-level combination, considering the game-level which originated the underlying predicted performance (**Figure 3**). To summarize, the first section of the RG creates a dictionary of learning potentials, which will inform the formulation of recommendations in the latter stages of the algorithm.

$$\delta_{G;L} = \rho_{\text{predicted for } G;L} - \rho_{\text{last registered for } G;L} \quad (1)$$

Second Stage: Cross-Session, Adaptive Errors

In a second stage of the RG, the Δ structure is modified to account for ζ - a collection of moving average errors for every game-level combination, specific to each player. More specifically, considering a given game-level combination, the corresponding ζ 's value - $\sigma_{G;L}$ - is the average of the last five differences between the predicted performance of the $(i + 1)$ th playthrough ($\rho_{predicted\ for\ G;L}^{T[i+1]}$) and the registered performance of the (i) th playthrough ($\rho_{registered\ for\ G;L}^{T[i]}$) (2). If the player has not gone through enough playthroughs for a 5-element average to be calculated, then $\sigma_{G;L}$ accounts for an inferior number of playthroughs (if the player has not had any playthrough at all, $\sigma_{G;L}$ is zero, thus not affecting the ζ structure). This procedure was implemented considering the interventive nature of the game suite, allowing adaptive recommendations based on the player's unique game history and learning profile. Programmatically, this modification originates a new dictionary of data points - Δ' -, which can be perceived as the predicted learning potentials corrected with a personalized factor of cross-session, temporal information.

$$\sigma_{G;L} = \left(\sum_{i=1}^5 \rho_{predicted\ for\ G;L}^{T[i+1]} - \rho_{registered\ for\ G;L}^{T[i]} \right) / 5 \quad (2)$$

Third Stage: Game Priority

To support the recommendation generation with theoretical foundations, Δ' is modified to account for a game priority list - a list which prioritizes the learning of more relevant EF first, and only then ER. This list is only composed of games, without a corresponding difficulty level. The list was supplied by EMPOWER's team of psychology experts and is defined in the following manner: Mushroom Hunters (sustained attention), WorM (working memory), RE Stroop (inhibitory control), ReFlex (cognitive flexibility), BEeHOLD (delay of gratification), Emotifest (3 emotion games - emotion naming, intensity, understanding and regulation). The game priority list is programmatically translated into a dictionary data structure which reflects a one-hot vector (a vector whose sum of elements is always equal to one) whose values are coefficients to be applied to Δ' , originating a new delta dictionary - Δ^* -, which can be interpreted as the predicted learning

potentials corrected with both a personalized factor of cross-session information and a game priority list (**Figure 3**).

Fourth Stage: Sorting and the 75% Performance Rule

Finally, the RG fetches the Δ^* values, sorting them in descending order. The algorithm then advances to a selection process: looping through the sorted entries and obtaining the highest verified delta value for each game, across all possible levels. Additionally, this selection process considers a 75% performance rule: for each game, if the last registered performance of a given difficulty level has not reached the 75% performance threshold, then the values of the sorted Δ^* structure corresponding to the same game, but subsequent levels will not be considered. As an example, if a player has yet to achieve a 75% or above performance in WorM's level 1, then the aforementioned selection process will disregard WorM's level 2 and level 3, with the algorithm not recommending these levels.

Fifth Stage: Final Recommendations

With the sorted Δ^* values, a new dictionary is formed - Δ_{final} -, which contains 9 entries (one for each game) of the highest predicted learning potentials, accounting for cross-session information and the game priority list. Besides the games, this data structure also contains the corresponding difficulty levels that lead to the highest learning potential. The inputted desired size of the recommendation list ($N_{\text{Recommendations}}$) is taken into account to discard unnecessary entries, thus shortening the Δ^* to a $N_{\text{Recommendations}}$ size. For the remainder of the text, we will consider $N_{\text{Recommendations}}$ as being equal to 3, since this is the number of recommendations displayed in the Teacher App. The final 3 Δ_{final} entries are thus converted into strings, displaying not only the suggested game but the recommended difficulty level and a brief justification, which, by default, highlights the role of the highest predicted learning potential in the recommendation process, promoting explainability. The RG thus reaches the end of its execution, conveying the resulting recommendations to the Teacher App.

Technical Caveats

Since the machine learning algorithm does not perform predictions for BEeHOLD and Emotifest due to a lack of training data, the RG possesses some caveats of relevant notice regarding these games. More specifically, since performance predictions cannot be directly employed for these games, their performance is estimated based on informed, theoretical principles, agreed upon during one of the regular project meetings. The RE Stroop's predicted performance (obtained by the machine learning algorithm) is thus exploited to estimate the performance of BEeHOLD, following a negative linear relation. Moreover, the ReFlex's predicted performance (obtained by the machine learning algorithm) is also exploited to estimate the performance of Emotifest, following a negative linear relation. These estimated performances are embedded within the deltas Δ data structure, and the remaining execution sequence of the RG occurs as described previously.

Finally, another edge case is worth mentioning: if the player has not played any games yet, then the predicted and registered performances will be nonexistent. In this case, the RG overwrites its normal execution and simply outputs a list of recommendations corresponding to the first difficulty level of the first 3 games of the game priority list, with the justification that at least one of these games must be played to kickstart the recommendation process grounded on the learning potential.

Example Scenario

Figure 4 illustrates how the RG works, with the assumptions that the player follows every supplied recommendation, considering a session as a set of 3 games. In session number 0 (when the player has not played any games yet), the RG suggests 3 games at difficulty level 1 (Mushroom Hunters, WorM, and RE Stroop), accounting for the game priority list and to kickstart the recommendation process. The player starts by playing these games and demonstrates a performance over 75% in all games except WorM. Consequently, the next set of recommendations includes Mushroom Hunters and RE Stroop at a higher level, additionally suggesting a new game - ReFlex. This is a common behaviour for most EF games (with ER, this is not verified every time due to the ML not predicting performances for these games): the joint efforts of the ML model and the RG algorithm ensure the player completes most level 1 games before moving on to increasing difficulties. The player once again follows the recommendations, achieving a score lower than 75% for RE Stroop, hence why a

new level 1 game is recommended after the second session (BEeHOLD), replacing RE Stroop. On the other hand, due to the continuously high-performance regarding Mushroom Hunters, the RG has maintained this game in its recommendations, with an increasing level of difficulty after each session. To summarize, the RG appropriately shifts recommendations to give priority to unplayed level 1 games, while promoting continuous learning “momentum” in games where high performances have been registered.

Figure 4 - Example scenario of communication between player's past game history and the recommendation generator

#6. Sensor Data

Beyond performance, the implemented algorithms enhance recommendations by incorporating data from two sensors: the Eye Tracker (ET), from which we extract information on saccade velocity, and the smartwatch, from which we collect Heart Rate (HR) data. To leverage this additional information, two Python modules classify sensor data into categories that represent the player's cognitive state during gameplay: the ET module and the HR module. Given the inherent variability of sensor data—caused by multiple factors—and the lack of a universally accepted standard link between sensor features and cognitive states, our multimodal approach (combining both sensors) aims to improve the reliability of sensor-based recommendations.

Data

Data was collected from a study conducted in primary schools in Portugal between May and June 2024. The sample included 33 neurotypical children aged 6 to 10 years. Each child played through all game levels in ascending order, with the games presented in a randomized sequence. Sensor data is collected using a smartwatch, particularly the Samsung Galaxy Watch 5 placed on the non-dominant wrist of the child for heart rate data with a frequency of 1Hz, and the Tobii Pro Nano EyeTracker attached to the computer for eye gaze data.

Heart Rate Module

Data from the smartwatch is fed into the HR module, which processes a list of heart rate values, a corresponding list of data quality values (provided by the watch itself), and timestamps.

Firstly, the HR module includes preprocessing of the raw data. Values with low data quality are excluded, and missing values are interpolated. If one recording has more than 30% of invalid data, it is excluded (labelled as “undefined state”). The HR feature we defined as most representative of the player’s cognitive state during the game is Heart Rate Variability (HRV), which is calculated as the Root Mean Square of Successive Differences (RMSSD) of heart rate values. This calculation is performed for each child, per game, and per level. Finally, the HR module classifies HRV in relation to game performance into four cognitive states: [“frustration”, “boredom”, “apathy”, “flow”]. The classification is data-driven, using a median split of HRV and performance data from the dataset. This approach follows the method used by authors in [4], and is illustrated in Figure 5. The classification is based on knowledge of physiological HRV fluctuations during cognitive tasks. The four emotional states are derived from the quadrant model, where:

- Q1 and Q4 (higher HRV) previous works show that high HRV values are related to lower cognitive effort in executive functions training tasks (i.e. children were “trying less hard” or less engaged with the task).
 - Q1 (**Boredom**): high performance with lower cognitive effort. The task might be too easy for the child and thus recommendation could include: i) jump to a more difficult level within the same game to try to increase the challenge to the child

- OR ii) given the good performance in this skill, recommendation of a next step might be to change the game to practise a different skill; this skill might be a weakness for the child and has a higher priority in the ordered list provided by the psychologists team or one that we do not have information about yet.
- Q4 (**Apathy**): low performance with lower cognitive effort. These children did not achieve the desired performance, but HRV information indicates that it might not be the best time to keep practising this skill, as the game is not engaging enough, or the child might be distracted. Recommendation could include: i) jump to a low level of a new game where this skill is practised differently to decrease the cognitive effort demanded while still practising this skill in a new setting that might be more engaging OR ii) jump to a game where skills on which we have no information about the child yet are practised and since the child is not very engaged this is a good time to do it.
 - Q2 and Q3: (lower HRV): previous works show that lower HRV values are related to higher cognitive effort in executive functions training tasks (i.e. children were “trying harder” or more engaged with the task).
 - Q2: high performance with higher cognitive effort (**Flow**). Recommendation could include keeping practising this skill in a more challenging context, either by i) playing the immediately more advanced level of the same game; OR ii) jumping to a game where this skill is also practised (in an equivalent or higher level)
 - Q3: low performance with higher cognitive effort (**Frustration**). Recommendations could include: i) play a lower level of the same game; ii) change to a game where this skill is also practised (equivalent or lower level).

Moreover, the HR model considers the most important feature of the last played game, and both models take the name of the last game played as the final input parameter (since the ET and HR classification is always relative to the last game). The difficulty level is disregarded and, once again considering data limitations, the models do not consider classifications regarding BEeHOLD and

Figure 5 - - Example of the performance vs. HRV values for the training dataset, for the inhibition game. The quadrants are split by the median values for each variable (in dotted lines).

Emotifest, defaulting to the “undefined state”.

Eye Tracker Module

The ET module is fed with a list of saccade velocity values, which are classified into “high effort” and “low effort” according to a threshold defined by the median split of the dataset. Saccade velocity corresponds to the speed of rapid eye movements between fixation points and is often used as an indicator of cognitive processes such as cognitive load, attention, and engagement. Faster saccades (higher velocity) tend to indicate lower effort (higher mean of saccade velocity values than median), while lower saccade velocity tends to indicate higher mental load and effort into cognitive processing (lower mean of saccade velocity values than median).

Future incorporations

Although currently the ET and HR classifications are merely informative and not utilized to support any further recommendation, the insights these models provide could be exploited by feeding their outputs into a global recommendation generator, which would take into account a recommendation solely based on performance and the engagement states measured by the ET and HR sensors. As an example, perhaps a player who is feeling extremely engaged (in a state of flow) should receive a recommendation to continue playing the current game, despite their predicted learning potential not demonstrating a high value in those circumstances. Contrarily, a player classified as being in a “bored” state could capitalize on being recommended another game, despite current learning potential.

#7 Conclusions

We designed theory-informed features in a multi-game suite, wherein the encompassing games correspond to gamified versions of standardized tasks for assessment of specific EF. One key limitation of our approach is related to the diversity of our sample. While including participants of varying age groups and diagnoses aligns with our goal of developing an inclusive and widely applicable game suite, it also introduces considerable variability in the data, making it harder to identify consistent patterns across the sample. This heterogeneity makes it difficult to isolate the sources of observed effects or performance issues, as it becomes unclear whether outcomes are driven by cognitive differences, age-related variability, diagnostic profiles, or other contextual factors.

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